

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EDUCATIONAL TOURISM AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN CALABAR MUNICIPAL LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The paper examined the relationship between educational tourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. The study adopted the survey research technique. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Educational Tourism and Economic Development Questionnaire (ETEDQ) was the instruments used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between educational tourism and the economic development in the study area.

Keyword: educational, tourism, economic development, Calabar Municipal, Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism has always been regarded as a means of economic modernization in the developed world but has not been seriously considered as a means of social and cultural modernization in most parts of Nigeria till date. The concept of socio economic modernization emphasize improvement in various indicators, including improvement in living conditions and the quality of life and wellbeing of the population.

Education tourism according to recorded literatures generates finance for infrastructure development and generally increases citizen's welfare. It has also influenced they Nigerian aviation industry

with the coming in of capital flights associated with overseas trip and an expansion of the same industry which had Nigerian Airways for a monopoly between the periods of 1985 to 1992. The increase is to the effect that as from 1992 there had been an influx of over 25 different carriers in the country. Tourist upon visitation, patronize local folk art such as straw baskets, hats, wooden carvings, ornaments, trinket and help improve the living standards of host areas (Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam & Oham, 2023). Tourism comes with a multiplier effect that rubs on other sectors of Nigeria's economy, namely: financial institutions, hospitals, transport, agriculture, environment and aviation (Ezenagu, 2013). Tourism is the main foreign exchange earner and the main source of job creation in the country. And so, income and prices are generally linked to the variables of demand for tourism.

Educational tourism, according to Patterson (2006) involves travel as part of the learning experience. Educational tourism is travel undertaken by an individual to a unique location for the purpose of formal or informal learning in various forms such as work experience, training in a new language, culinary training, medical tourism, cultural tours, and professional development. School, university trips and specialty camps are also educational travel (Sayre & King, 2010). It based on the above background that the researchers' intends to investigate the relationship between educational tourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria.

Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam and Oham (2023) posited that education tourism is the sector with the biggest employer of labour in Nigeria as it is generating employment for millions of people and its effect rubs on every aspect of people from taxi drivers to Bank managers (Tunde, 2012) in 2002 the tourism industry generated an estimated 199 million jobs - one in every 13 jobs worldwide. Nigeria as at 2011, the Travel and Tourism industry was forecast to directly generate a total of 897, 500 jobs in 2012, and that happens to comprises of 1.4 % of total employment in Nigeria.

Calabar Municipal has the potentials to become one of the leading tourist destinations due to her rich cultural heritage, tourism sites, cuisines, attractions etc. and traces of the different types of tourism being found in it, has stimulated the development of a variety of allied infrastructure and facilities such as Calabar International Convention Centre (CICC), National Museum Calabar, sport stadium, airport and others, owing all the above listed tourism locations and facilities, one wonders if tourism contributes to the economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River state. Tourism is the number one employer of labour in the world and jobs created by tourism spreads across the economy in areas of construction, telecommunications, retail and manufacturing, thus, creating jobs in large number for young people, women, and minorities whether in small or medium size companies.

The advantages and potentials portrayed by tourism in the development of Calabar Municipal are without doubt immense. The proper utilization of the tourism sector may open doors to different opportunities in the local government, the State and the country at large (the gap this research study intends to fill). But there have been a recent trend of the government complaining of lack of revenue for the development of the local government, the state and other agencies including tourism organizations, whereas tourism is supposed to attract revenue to the State based on the demand for tourism resources. The local government has struggled in carrying out and finishing their existing projects due to finances, delay in the payment of salaries due to lack of funds. These trends have therefore led to a need to study the potentials of tourism in boosting economic development. This study is therefore set out with the intention of examining the impact of tourism on the economic development of Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. The following research question was posed to direct the study; how does educational tourism relate to economic development in Calabar Municipal?

1.2 Theoretical frame work

The following theories were considered to back up the research:

1.2.1 The modernization theory by Rostow (1990)

The modernization theory was postulated by Walt Whitman Rostow in the year 1990. The theory is also called Rostow's theory of growth and development and it outlines the various stages that are involved

in developing tourism projects until they become generally acceptable for the purpose they are meant for. This developing strategies for theory was proposed by Winton in 1954 when he was building stadia for Nigerians. Modernization is an important process due to its systematic and transformative nature that builds change into the system. One of the principal applications of modernization theory has been in economic field and public policy. The economic theory of modernization anchors on five stages of development as follows: the traditional society (pre-industrial), preconditions for takeoff the takeoff process, the drive maturity and high mass consumption (Rostow, 1990).

The tenet of modernization theory or Rostow's theory of growth and development is that there is a natural inertia that needs to be overcome before self-sustained development can take place. They include built up transport, investment enhanced organization and production in agriculture and increase in imports particularly capital. These three factors are seen as the preconditions for take-off. Once these pre-conditions for takeoff have been met and take-off started, the economy is deemed to be on a route of self-sustained consistent growth and it will lead to mass consumption. In order to maintain the self-sustained consistent growth, good human relations and marketing strategies must be maintained. The application of this theory shows the sequential process for tourism project development. The standard stated in this development process aids in the provision of infrastructure to the people, and social amenities to the sites and the environs, and provide the tourists coming and interacting communities with good roads, communication network, banks, hospitals and other strategies to sustain and maintain the site. It also guides in protecting and preserving such sites. All these eventually create jobs for people and leads to other economic and environmental effects.

1.2.2 Malthusian theory of economic development (1798)

The Malthusian theory was propounded by Thomas Robert Malthus in the year 1798. Malthus contends that the process of economic development is not automatic. Rather conscious, deliberate efforts are needed to bring it about. For instance, Malthus explains that mere increase in population cannot by itself lead to economic development unless there is increase in effective demand. He rejects Say's Law which says supply creates its own demand and that savings are automatically invested and constitutes a demand for capital goods. Malthus' important contribution shows that savings in the sense of not consuming is a mere negative act and instead of creating more demand it will lead to a decline in effective demand. Only savings which are furnished by increased gains and are invested create an effective demand. Thus, according to him, abstinence on the part of capitalists, far from accelerating economic growth, will in itself retard it. Hence, Malthus brings out an important fact expand that in advanced economy consumption, saving and investment all should simultaneously.

Malthus attaches great importance to the accumulation of capital for economic development. He regards capital as indispensable to development. According to him, no permanent and continued increase of wealth can take place without a continued increase of capital. Besides, Malthus underlined the importance of foreign trade for speeding up economic development. Foreign trade provides incentives for investing, since it leads to the extension of the market for the goods produced and for greater division of labour resulting in increased output.

Tourism also helps economic activities to grow in a given country. Most people go into other countries for business tourism and they invest in such countries. The more tourists are found in a country, the more economic activities that take place. The population of foreign people in a country who depend on the country's resources can enhance economic development.

There is another important fact brought out by Malthusian analysis of economic growth, namely, the structured change that takes place in the process of economic development i.e., a decline in the relative importance of agriculture as the economy moves forward. We know that economic development in developing countries is regarded as synonymous with the development of industries. Malthus' contribution to economic growth contains several elements that are relevant to the developing economies. His emphasis

on production and distribution, capital accumulation and the creation of congenial non-economic factors is as valid today as was in his time.

The implication of the theory to this study is that, tourism increases the number of people in a given state. Most of these tourists have high demand for local resources. When local resources are highly demanded, demand becomes effective. Effective demand increases economic development and also increases investment opportunities. As tourists are attracted to tourist destinations, they contribute to increase in population of such destination and hence raise the effective demand of goods and services in such areas. The producers of such goods and services demanded by tourists in a bid to maximize profit will demand for more labour to increase in supply and this consequently leads to employment generation.

1.3 Statement of hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide this study;

There is no significant relationship between educational tourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal.

1.4 Justification/Significance of the study

The research work will be of benefit to the government of Cross River State and her indigene because of the tourism potentials inherent of the State. The research work will also help researchers and even the students especially those in tourism and eco-management. The findings of this study will be of relevance to the governments across the entire world as the findings of this study will showcase reasons for government investment in the tourism sector. The host communities under study will benefit from the findings of this study as the government can see the tourism potential of the communities. Finally this research work will serve as a source of information and guide to researchers' in the field of tourism for future use.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Educational tourism and economic development

2.1.1 Conceptual review

Travel for the sake of education has a long history (Bodger, Bodger & Frost, 2004). It was during the middle years of the nineteenth century, and in parallel with the beginnings of formalised education for various age groups from young to old, that the practice was established of townspeople and city dwellers making day visits to the country for self-improvement. The modern-day learning vacation concept is known as educational travel.

According to Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam and Oham (2023) educational tourism as a concept, therefore, refers to common topics, such as formal education, travel, tourism and skills, but precise attributes have yet to be agreed upon. The ongoing debate concerns the motivation of the learner/traveler, the links between formal and informal learning, and the relation between tourism and education. Educational tourists (students, adults, and seniors) are those respondents who indicated that they took part in study tours or who attended workshops to learn new skills or improve existing ones while on vacation.

According to the Canberra Australian Capital Tourism Report, an education tourist is defined as a traveler aged 15 years or above whose main reason for coming to the host country is education and the length of stay is less than twelve months. Educational travel of this sort really developed from the 1960s onwards. Initially it was a function of educational institutions, for example: university extra-mural departments which added a field trip to a class that had run through the winter months so that students could see for themselves the objects of their study (Bodger, Bodger & Frost, 2004). The term education tourism or educational tourism refers to any program in which participants travel to a as a group with the primary purpose of engaging in a learning experience directly related to the location. According to Bodger, Bodger and Frost (2004), today the term educational travel could be taken to mean any of a spectrum of travel opportunities: from the school child going on a study holiday to a Mediterranean Cruise with a guest

lecturer, or a language student studying abroad, other educational study tours, travel packages for adults where education is a major or the prime objective.

Tourist activity undertaken by those who are undertaking an overnight vacation and those who are undertaking an excursion for whom education and learning is a primary (education first segment) or secondary (tourism first segment) part of their trip (Ritchie, Carr & Cooper, 2003). A form of tourist's experience that explicitly aims to provide structured learning in situ through active and engaged intellectual praxis. Learning is explicit and core to the delivery of the product.

Organized trip led by skilled guides where leisure-travel activities and learning processes occur simultaneously through interaction between related stakeholders (participants, tour operators/leaders, and local community) as part of the total experience. The educational tourism experience occurs within a certain period of time (minimum of 24h away from home) and generally ensues in an informal setting. Educational tourism is identified as comprising a variety of activities including international exchange-student programmes, sabbatical and staff exchanges, educational tours, school trips, study tours, short courses, language courses, special interest tours, conferences, academic colloquiums, ongoing adult education programmes, summer and winter schools, international voluntary and gap- year programmes, development practice training, internships, sports coaching seminars, cultural history tours (Ozşen, 2012). He stated that educational tourism comes in a variety of formats such as school trips, alternative spring break travel experiences, study abroad experiences, seminar vacations, skill enhancement vacations and educational cruises. He concludes that all forms of educational tourism have a number of items in common.

Obrien and Mojdeh (2013) argued that international students can contribute to the local economy through on-campus spending directly related to their studies; off-campus spending on housing, food, books, transportation, clothing and entertainment; contribution to the local tourism industry through domestic travel and other tourist activities and non-educational tourism spending by students, visiting friends and relatives (VFR) and the return visits of alumni.

International students can also have a direct economic impact on tourism in the host country. In Australia, Weaver (2001) in Asiedu (2008) found that all the international students of the sample group visited the local tourist attractions or other regions, mostly on their own initiative. Moreover, as mentioned above, visiting friends and relatives can also have a substantial impact on the local economy, as they usually add tours of the destination and nearby regions. According to Asiedu (2008), these visits are one of the foremost motivators in tourism. Particularly in non-urban areas, tourism may contribute to demographic stability and socioeconomic sustainability. This type of tourism has the potential to generate local prosperity through decent jobs and better incomes. The presence of international students at a destination creates new entrepreneurial and employment opportunities related to the student's expenses at the local level. In some cases, new services are built to respond to students needs for housing, cultural activities, and leisure and entertainment opportunities.

2.1.2 Empirical review

Muhammad, Farzana, Muhammad and Ismail (2023) carry out systematic literature review (SRL) examines the impact of English educational tourism (EET) on the growth of local Small-Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Through a comprehensive search of academic databases and systematic assessment of study quality, a total of 49 studies were selected for inclusion. The studies varied in design, location, and intervention, but all focused on the relationship between English educational tourism and the growth of local SMEs. This SLR focuses on the typology of SMEs in EET, its impact on rural economy and local community empowerment, and SMEs' challenges in growing their businesses. The findings suggest that English educational tourism can have a positive impact on local SMEs and rural communities, including increased revenue, community empowerment, cultural preservation, and poverty reduction. However, it is crucial to ensure that the benefits of EET are distributed fairly and that local communities are actively involved in the decision-making process to maximize positive impacts and mitigate potential negative impacts. Overall, the results suggest that English educational tourism can be a promising strategy for

promoting the growth of local economy, but more research is needed to fully understand the conditions under which this impact is most effective.

The study of Onnoghen, Unimtiang, Ogban, Ogbaji, Iyam and Oham (2023) investigated ecotourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of this study, a null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study. A review of related literature was carried out based on the variable of this study. The survey research design was considered useful for the study. The research adopted multiple sampling approaches. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 232 subjects used as sample in each ward in the Local Government Area. A twenty-item modified four (4) points Likert scale questionnaire titled Ecotourism and Economic Development Questionnaire (ETEDQ) was the instruments used for gathering data for the study. To test the hypotheses formulated for the study, Pearson's product moment correlation statistical tools was used for data analysis. The hypothesis formulated was tested at 0.05 alpha level. The results from data analysis and hypothesis testing indicated that there is a significant relationship between ecotourism and the economic development in the study area.

Abu Samah and Ahmadian (2013) conducted a cross sectional study aimed at assessing the impacts of educational tourism on the residents in the Klang Valley, Malaysia. Data was collected from 700 respondents using structured questionnaire from the Klang Valley and Nilai. Pearson product moment correlation analysis and multilinear regression was used in analyzing the acquired data. The study findings revealed that there is significant positive moderate relationship between attitude, environmental impact, economic impact, and socio-cultural impact and practice. The study further found that socio-cultural and economic impact of educational tourism, and local community attitude has significantly contributed to residents' practice to educational tourists in the Klang Valley. The results of this study present practical information on sustainable educational programs for both the Ministry of Higher Education and the Ministry of Tourism.

Hussein, Kusairi and Ismail (2021) also conducted a research on the impact of educational tourism on economic growth: a panel data analysis. A panel dataset of 11 countries was selected as the main group in international education exporter for the years 2002-2017 and this study utilized static panel data analysis. The results found that educational tourism and exports have positive impact on economic growth. The study also found that there is a country specific effect through different constant. This study proved that other than exports of goods, certain countries can benefit from the educational tourism sector as the new engine of economic sustainability.

Furthermore, Ozsen (2012) conducted a research aimed at determining the socio-cultural, economic and environmental effects of the students of EMU on the local people of Famagusta in North Cyprus. The qualitative approach was used in order to obtain the necessary information. Data were collected through in-depth interviews from the viewpoint of local people. The respondents were local people of Famagusta city of North Cyprus. The result of findings revealed that there were positive and negative influences of educational tourism in terms of socio-cultural, economic and environmental effects on the local community of Famagusta. The proliferation of income, performance in service sectors, job opportunities and improvement of construction sector were the economic positive influences observed from the data. In addition, the results of gathered from the interviewer's demonstrated that the educational tourism in Famagusta led to the increase of prices in general. The results of data also showed that educational tourism caused to changes in family values, disruption of social bonds, and increase in alcohol and drug consumption/selling, opening of bet offices, increase of traffic accidents, theft incidents and changes of the community's style of eating, drinking and clothing. Educational tourism also led to environmental problems such as an increase of traffic jams, unplanned construction and infrastructure, water, electricity problems, air and noise pollution. The study concluded that although host population perceived many socio-cultural, environmental and some economic problems with educational tourism development in their community,

overall they were happy about the economic benefits it brought to their community and thus about the development of educational tourism in general.

Similarly, Matahir and Tang (2017) conducted a research aimed at assessing the effect of educational tourism on Malaysia's economic growth. The study used the sample from 2002:Q1 to 2014:Q4. The newly developed Bayer-Hanck combined tests for cointegration and the Granger causality test were employed to examine the long-run and causal relationships among the variables. The empirical findings suggest that economic growth, educational tourism, and other determinants are cointegrated. Educational tourism has a bi-directional causal relationship with economic growth in the short-run but there is a unidirectional Granger causality runs from educational tourism to economic growth. The study provides an essential insight for Malaysia to create policies that promote educational tourism, thereby encouraging economic growth in the long-run.

The present study appraised one type of tourism, educational tourism. Each poses great potential as can be seen in the literature. Nevertheless, while tourism development is widely recognized for enhancing the quality of life, those societies in the developed world, for many developing nations such as Nigeria; it has a critical role to play in the nation's economy.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research design

The research design adopted for this study is the correlational research design. It involves the collection of data to accurately and objectively describe existing phenomena. This design is employed because the study intends to gather information ready existing among the population under study. Moreover adopting the survey helps the researcher to gather required data from the sampled respondents and generalize it to a large population.

The area adopted for this study is Calabar Municipal of Cross River State. Calabar Municipal lies between latitude $04^{\circ} 57' 06''$ North of the equator and longitude $08^{\circ} 19' 30''$ East of the Greenwich Meridian. The targeted populations for this research are adults in all the schools, hotels and banks in Calabar Municipality, Cross River State. The researcher considered males and females above the ages of 18 years to participate in the research because of their ability to understand and their knowledge of current trends. Calabar Municipal has a total population of 419,643 people from 2022 population estimates.

The sampling procedure adopted for this study is the stratified sampling, simple random sampling and accidental sampling techniques respectively. The stratified sampling was applied to stratify the population according to the target population. The simple random sampling technique was used to select ten (10) schools, hotels and banks from Calabar Municipal Local Government Area, This was done using the hat and draw method. Here, the names of the schools, hotels and banks were written on papers and folded in paper balls and put in a container. The researcher blindly picked one ball at a time until the 10 schools, hotels and banks for the research was completed.

In selecting the respondents that would be used for the study, the proportional simple random sampling technique was adopted to select 0.5% of respondents in each of the selected school, hotel and bank. Finally, the researchers adopted the accidental sampling technique to administer their questionnaire to the respondents in the selected communities. Only those willing to participate in the study were given the opportunity to do so. These techniques were adopted to avoid possible bias. The sample of this study comprise of 232 respondents selected from 10 schools, hotels and banks in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. They consist of both male and female residents in the sampled schools, hotels and banks.

The instrument employed for data collection was a questionnaire titled, Education Tourism and Economic Development Questionnaire (ETEDQ) designed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A was design to collect the respondent's demographic data such as sex and age, while section B comprises twenty (20) items designed to measure educational tourism and economic development of Calabar Municipal. The questionnaire was the main instrument used for data collection. The data used for this research was sourced from primary sources. The Primary data were

gathered through the respondents from face to face administration of questionnaires. This is because questionnaire can be more easily quantified and analysed. The construction of the questionnaire succumbs to the rule of simplicity, clarity, precision and relevant so as to elicit the quantitative data it seeks. The questionnaire contained close ended questions to aid the respondent in minimize the risk of misinterpretation and allow them to understand the question carefully in order to give the correct response the questionnaire administered. Out of the 232 copies of questionnaire administered in the study, a total of 232 questionnaires were returned. This represents a response percentage rate of 100%. After collecting the questionnaire, scores were assigned to each item according to the sections. The four point modified Likert close ended scale was employed in this study. The scale is as follows;

Strongly Agree (SA)	=	4
Agree	=	3
Disagree (D)	=	2
Strongly Disagree (SD)	=	1

The researchers' adopted Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis and found it to be the most appropriate statistical tool for measuring the variables under study. Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) program version 23. Results were presented in tables as well as inferential statistics as the research hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance (i.e. 95% confidence interval).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Presentation of results

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between educational tourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal. This hypothesis was tested using Pearson product moment correlation analysis. This is because the independent and dependent variables were both measured continuously. The result of the analysis is as presented in table 1.

TABLE 1.

Result of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis of the relationship between educational tourism and economic development of Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State

Variables	N	X	S.D	r-value	Sig.
Educational tourism	232	17.31	2.570		
Economic development	232	15.11	1.363	.497**	.000

**Correlation is significant at .01 level, df=230, critical r=.158.

The result presented in table 1, shows the correlation between educational tourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area. It showed a calculated r-value of .497 which is statistically greater than the critical r-value or .158 at .05 level of significance with 230 degrees of freedom. As a result of this, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld. The implication of this is that educational tourism has a significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State.

5 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The hypothesis states that educational tourism has no significant relationship with economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. This hypothesis was

however rejected on the ground that the calculated r-value of .497 was found to be significantly greater than the critical r-value of .158. The implication of this result is that educational tourism has significant effect on economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State.

This finding is in tandem with a study by Abu Samah and Ahmadian (2013) whose cross sectional study aimed at assessing the impacts of educational tourism on the residents in the Klang Valley, Malaysia. The study found a significant relationship between educational tourism and economic development. Similarly,

This finding is also in tandem with the study by Jussein, Kusairi and Ismail (2021) whose research on the impact of educational tourism on economic growth: a panel data analysis agree with the findings of the present study. This study proved that other than exports of goods, certain countries can benefit from the educational tourism sector as the new engine of economic sustainability. Furthermore, the result is also in line with the study of Ozsen (2012) whose study aimed at determining the socio-cultural, economic and environmental effects of the students of EMU on the local people of Famagusta in North Cyprus also agrees with the findings of the present study as it found out that there were positive and negative influences of educational tourism in terms of socio-cultural, economic and environmental effects on the local community of Famagusta.

6 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the result that emerged from the analysis of data collected for this study, the following conclusion was made: There is significant relationship between educational tourism and economic development in Calabar Municipal Local Government Area of Cross River State. Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion made thereof, the following recommendations were made: proper education of the residents on the relevance of tourism to economic development in the local government to improve their interest in participating in tourism related activities. The government of the State should invest more on education to attract tourist from all over the world.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

One of the problems encountered while carrying out this research is that the researchers were always present in every occasions to enhance positive collection of data from the respondents. More so, in order to get accurate data, the researcher had to plead with the respondents to be honest in their response. This makes the researchers to always go an extra mile to pacify them. However, it is imperative to mention that an encountered limitation does not distort the validity of the finding, because the limitations were overcome. Based on the findings of the study, the following suggestions are made for further studies:

- 1 A similar study should be conducted to cover other variables not investigated by this study.
- 2 The use of larger sample to widen the scope of the study should be encourage as to investigate further analysis, generalization and expansion of the frontiers of the subject of investigation.
- 3 A replication of this study should be carried out again covering the entire State.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Our paper, the relationship between educational tourism and the economic development of Calabar Municipal, Cross River State, Nigeria, is unique and has never been published, we certify. Every piece of information is true, responsibly gathered, and properly cited from outside sources. The text guarantees participant confidentiality by adhering to ethical requirements. We promise not to post it anywhere without editorial permission if it is accepted. We are grateful for the assistance we had during the study. This contribution demonstrates our dedication to openness and academic honesty.

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